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Rebels with a Cause? Supporting Library and Academic-led Open Access Publishing

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Abstract

The authors, who all have experience with academic publishing, outline the landscape of new university and academic-led publishing, before discussing four pressing and often recurring issues that are often used to challenge the existence of new university and academic-led publishing ventures. The authors provide examples of how, albeit differing in scale, form and ambition, these new presses are adhering to academic quality standards and often surpassing them. This article is an elaborated and extended version of a panel discussion held at the Annual LIBER Conference 2018 in Lille, France (Deville et. al. 2018).

Keywords

Open Access publishing

Library publishing

Academic-led publishing

Introduction

Open access for monographs is mandated by only a few funders, such as Austria, the Netherlands, and the Wellcome Trust in the UK. However, in a rapidly evolving landscape, recent announcements concerning an open access mandate for monographs from Research England (formerly HEFCE) at the UP Redux conference in February 2018 and from Madame Frederique Vidal, the French Minister of Higher Education, Research and Innovation at the LIBER conference in July have shown an increasing open access commitment for scholarly books across Europe (Vidal, 2018). Furthermore the recently published report on the “Visibility of Open Access Monographs in a European Context” (Neylon et al., 2018) from the EU funded OPERAS project shows a growing commitment on a European level. And now there is Plan S. An ambitious plan initiated and launched on September 4th, 2018, by the cOAlition S, a consortium with the European Research Council (ERC) and more than a dozen national research funders (Science Europe, 2019). The plan is structured around 10 principles for open access publishing although the focus lies on journal publishing, monographs are acknowledged but given more time for a transition to open access. As stated: “cOAlition S will, at a later stage, issue guidance on Open Access monographs and book chapters” (cOAlition S, 2018). Within the context of Plan S, it is most likely that open access monographs will in one way or the other be mandated at some point in time and at least by the funders that take part in this coalition.

In recent years, several reports have highlighted the growth of new innovative publishing operations in Europe. In the UK, Jisc’s *Changing publishing ecologies landscape* study (Adema & Stone, 2017) showed a discernible increase in new publishing initiatives and academic-led presses over the last few years. The *Academic books and their future* report (Jubb, 2017) highlighted that many of these new scholarly communication models were closely linked to university libraries, and almost all were committed to open access journal and monograph publishing. Regarding open access monographs, the *Knowledge Exchange landscape study on open access and monographs* (Ferber, Pinter & Stern, 2017) was an in-depth report, which compared and contrasted access to books across eight European countries. Many of the presses engaging with new models for open access book publishing highlighted in this study are academic- or library-led. In this article we define Library-led New University Presses as a “set of activities led by college and university libraries to support the creation, dissemination, and curation of scholarly, creative, and/or educational works” (Lippincott, 2016). Academic-led publishing can be described as “a publishing initiative set-up and run by academics. Academic-led presses are most often not-for profit, independent, highly ideological entities, set up to provide an alternative publication route to the commercial presses or to support the open access publishing of books for example” (Adema J., in Stone, 2018).

Concerns regarding the perceived lack of professionalism and quality of these new presses were expressed during the second University Press Redux Conference in February 2018 and at the open access monographs event for learned societies and subject associations held by the Universities UK Open Access monograph working group and the Arts and Humanities Alliance (AHA) in September 2018. This view is highlighted in the 2018 position paper by the British Academy, which states that.

“A further risk that needs to be taken into account is the equivalent in the domain of book publishing of the proliferation of new online journals with lower standards of peer review and editing that attended the move to OA for articles. It would be unfortunate if OA for books came to be associated even to a small degree with a new form of vanity publishing” (British Academy, 2018).

Indeed, Jubb highlights a number of issues regarding these innovative ventures. The *Academic Books and their future report* expresses concerns that many are still relatively small scale startups with few staff and small numbers of journal and monograph publications. In particular, the report suggested that “at present they have more in common with the world of self-publishing than with the more established presses” (Jubb, 2017, p.44)

This article challenges these perceptions. The authors, who all have experience with academic publishing, outline the landscape of new university and academic-led publishing, before discussing four pressing and often recurring issues that are often used to challenge the existence of new university and academic-led publishing ventures. The authors provide examples of how, albeit differing in scale, form and ambition, these new presses are adhering to academic quality standards and often surpassing them. In this article we focus on book publishing, but given that many of these challenges are the same as for journal publishing, we draw on experiences/data with journals where relevant. However, there are also differences, especially when it comes to the challenges of professionalism, proliferation, quality and discoverability.

Challenge 1: Professionalism

Given the recent surge of newly established publishers with a renewed interest for non-profit publishing models and open access, it is perhaps unsurprising to see a backlash from the publishing establishment. One form this has taken are allegations that these publishers either lack the professionalism or resources to deliver high-quality digital publications; a noteworthy example is this blog post posted on Scholarly Kitchen by a former CEO of Encyclopedia Britannica (Esposito, 2015). Indeed, such critical scrutiny could be considered a healthy reaction, contributing to ensuring that published outputs contributes to developments in the field of publishing rather than any form of regression.

However, there have been recent developments that go some way to countering such charges. For example, The Library Publishing Coalition announced the first library publishing curriculum modules in 2018. Co-written by library publishers and representatives from the American Association of University Presses (AAUP), the curriculum is explicitly aimed at supporting the further professional development of library publishers (Schlosser, 2018). Furthermore, in 2018, the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) announced a new Library Publishing Special Interest Group, which held its inaugural workshop in 2019 (IFLA, 2019).

Publishers of books contribute to the process of disseminating academic findings by providing services for editing, typesetting, formats for both print and online publishing, distribution and promotion of the content. Authors and readers expect these services to be performed with professionalism and that the publisher will be expert in providing the tools and technique used to produce a book that is affordable, aesthetically pleasing and easy for readers to find and read. Other characteristics of a reliable publisher are accountability and ethical responsibility as well as having competent staff to guide authors through the process. Critics of academic-led or library publishing have voiced their doubt and questioned whether small organisations can become as reliable. Advocates for academic-led and library publishing on the other hand claim that the publishing services could serve the author community better as they are often more closely integrated with the university. If the publishers' staff are academics themselves or work in an academic environment, they would be more in tune with the needs of authors and the working terms. Publishing houses hosted by university libraries are also increasing, and librarians as a profession have a variety of skill sets that are valuable when planning an organisation for disseminating scholarly works (see also professional development from the LPC above). Librarians' engagement in the changing landscape of access to scholarly material also plays a role in developing skills such as licensing management, discovery and dissemination, publishing analytics, leadership, digital information expertise and service integration (Ayriss & Ignat, 2018; Skinner et al., 2014).

We would like to argue that the academic-led and library publishers can provide the same reliable services as traditional publishers by using skill sets that are already represented in the academic organisations, which could in the long run create more sustainable workflows and reliable service than the traditional market-driven publishers may not be as inclined to provide without a considerable return on investment.

Contracts and licensing

Contracts to regulate the agreement between the author and the publisher are at the core of publishing, as the terms of the contract stipulates the nature of the service provided to the author and how the end product can be used and disseminated. For library-led publishers, this could easily be a task for the collection management team. Libraries have long been negotiating and agreeing licenses with publishers and other vendors, managing patron licences where applicable. Professional advice is thus available within the package of services that libraries provide for researchers anyway. Academic-led publishers would, therefore, be in a position to give adequate support. There are also examples of smaller publishers working together and sharing services and to address for example the need for a sound foundation for licensing of open access books as well as the possibility to disseminate and sell hard copies on a global scale.

Workflow & infrastructure

To publish a book is not simply an assembly line from the point of entry of academic content to the exit point when it is published online and/or in print. Book publishing is much more complex than that, which could explain why many authors only trust their content to be managed by a traditional publisher that they believe can accommodate this need. However, a large and complex publisher organisation is likely to also be rather expensive, a critique often voiced by funding organisations and other academic stakeholders. For academic-led or library publishers this is an area where there are lots of opportunities to build sustainable and professional workflows by collaboration (Taylor & Jensen, 2018). Others such as OAPEN in the Netherlands and OpenEdition in France have also contributed to facilitating book workflows by providing platforms for global distribution of digital books and metadata structures that work with other information management systems (OAPEN. (n.d.), OpenEdition. (n.d.)). Furthermore, there are presses who outsource certain parts of the publishing process elements through a variety of publishing services such as the Ubiquity Partner Network (2019), Open Library of Humanities' Janeway platform (Eve, 2018), or Vega (2018) – a collaboration between American university presses. Many major publishers do exactly the same when they outsource their technical workflows to specialised services companies, so the collaborative method is well tested. In the UK, Jisc has developed a dynamic purchasing service (DPS) for new university presses to assist with the procurement of publishing services that support workflows from participating suppliers (Milloy, 2018).

Academic liaison & support

The relation between publishers and researchers are also at the heart of academic publishing. As academics can often choose which publisher they would like to work with, this is something that this is already an area of strength for librarians. For example, building relationships with researchers at every stage of their career is part

of the bread and butter of librarianship. Librarians often help researchers in the writing process, especially early career researchers via writing skills workshops, 'shut-up and write' sessions and support for student publishing (Stone, Jensen & Beech, 2016; Taylor & Jensen, 2018)

Marketing & Analytics

Marketing is an example of a skill that librarians have developed in recent years, and such activities is now commonplace in libraries (Brewerton, 2003). Furthermore, much of the marketing for individual titles relies on the networks of the authors and journal editors and via social media channels, which takes us back to academic liaison. This is exemplified by many major publishers who often send a marketing plan to both journal and book authors in order to fully utilize authors networks.

New initiatives such as the OA Book Watch project, which was discussed during the Knowledge Exchange workshop on open access monographs, aims to "monitor progress, identify good practices, examples, and business cases, and to provide a tool for funders and policy makers" (Adema, 2019, p.3).

Dissemination and discovery

It could be argued that librarians often know more about this side of publishing than many publishers. Cataloguing/metadata creation is part of the day-to-day functions of a library. At the 2018 Jisc CNI leadership conference, Susan Gibbons, University Librarian and Deputy Provost at Yale University noted that the library performs this function for Yale University Press (Gibbons, 2018). Library publishers are also in the unique position of understanding the issues of open access discovery too, this idea is developed further below.

Developing professionalism

The added value and professionalism provided by often small-scale academic- and library-led publishing entities are the ability to adapt quickly to circumstances and demands that are closer to the needs of the authors of articles, books and chapters. For example, by making use of new innovative and cost-effective infrastructure.

It should be noted that many well established presses in the United States report directly to the library (Watkinson, 2014; Gibbons, 2018). So it is not surprising to see this model adopted in the UK and the rest of Europe. However, that does not mean they are library exclusive initiatives. Although a press may report to the library, the vast majority in the UK are academic-led via a steering group or editorial board. Often these groups are chaired by a pro vice chancellor for research or equivalent position (UCL, 2019; University of Huddersfield, n.d.).

Furthermore many library-led presses are managed by staff with publishing backgrounds. For example, Westminster, Huddersfield and UCL presses in the UK, Uopen Journals at Utrecht University in the Netherlands and Stockholm University Press in Sweden.

Challenge 2: Scale

A view across the landscape of scholarly publishing highlights two trends seemingly in tension with one another. On the one hand, while we very much welcome the increasing diversity of new open access book publishers, this proliferation goes against trend towards consolidation that the commercial academic publishing industry has witnessed in recent years with the associated expansion of logics of closure, centralisation, and proprietary rights management (Larivière, 2015, Greenfield, 2014). One consequence is that these new publishers tend to operate at a much smaller scale than the traditional publishers that have historically dominated the marketplace. The result is an increasing number of publishers,¹ the majority of which publish far fewer books than their larger commercial cousins, often dependent to a significant extent on volunteer labour with few or no full time paid staff, and often without access to many of the the systems and forms of expertise – whether for example relating to production, distribution, marketing – which legacy publishers have built up over the years.

These issues are a challenge for many if not all of the new wave of open access publishers as well as all small publishers, one which they are grappling with in various ways. However, in assessing the merits and demerits of open access book publishing we suggest that a focus on scale alone may occlude at least two ways in which new open access publishers are transforming academic publishing not *in spite* of their small scale but *because of it*. These relate, first, to the increasing tendency for open access publishers to work not in isolation from one another but collaboratively, a tendency we refer to as *scaling small* and, second, to the way in which operating at a smaller scale does not decrease but increase the possibility of innovating with publishing practices.

Collaboration

One of the most noteworthy features about academic- and library-led book publishing in recent years has been the tendency for publishers to look to each other for forms of support. This, both implicitly and more explicitly, marks a rejection of the logics of competition that characterise commercial publishing. A number of the publishers referenced here are, for instance, part of and contributors to the Radical

¹ For instance, Research by Tanner (2016) shows that in the UK there were 8,513 books submitted to Main Panel D (Arts and Humanities) for the 2014 Research Excellence Framework. Although 46% of all books submitted were from ten publishers (3,926), the total number of publishers returned to Panel D was 1,180. It into this healthy 'long tail' in which Scholar- and Library-led publishers fit.

Open Access collective (2019), whose explicit goal is to build ‘horizontal alliances’. Part of the function of the collective is to act as a repository for tools and forms of expertise that can be shared across the open access publishing community. Another prominent example is the recently formed ScholarLed collective (2018), which at the time of writing counts six presses of small sized presses all led by academics. Their explicit aim is to focus the attention of the open access community on the need to open up not just academic content, but the infrastructures of publishing. As Bilder et al. (2015) argue, “[e]verything we have gained by opening content and data will be under threat if we allow the enclosure of scholarly infrastructures”. This is a particularly pressing issue in the context of large commercial entities taking over important community-built platforms for open research (e.g. Elsevier’s takeovers of be.press and SSRN and many more examples exist (Bosman, J. & Kramer, B. (2016)). What such instances of collaboration promise is the possibility of generating the economies of scale necessary to develop the infrastructure necessary to be successful in the landscape of contemporary publishing, while allowing small publishers to retain their unique identities and forms of engagement with the academic and non-academic communities they serve. In this sense, collaboration represents a future of academic- and library-led publishing that, while not yet fully realised, offers considerable grounds for hope.

Innovation

The second key advantage of operating at a smaller scale is the organisational flexibility it affords which, as noted, the collaborative models that are being developed allow to be retained. In particular, partly as they are less constrained by forms of organisational path dependence and lock-in (e.g. Sydow et al., 2009) than most commercial publishers, publishers have shown themselves far more ready to innovate when it come to book publishing, in terms of both the content of books and the mechanics of publishing itself. With regards to the former, one of punctum books’ *raison d’être*, for instance, is promoting “the work that everybody wants to do but isn’t allowed to do” (Adema & Stone, 2017, p.45).

Open access publishers have also repeatedly experimented with the form of books: one of Punctum’s imprints, Hyperrhiz Electric, focuses explicitly on publishing “long-form scholarly projects built partially or wholly in online format: electric objects that cannot be printed” (punctum books, n.d). Open Humanities Press’ ‘Liquid Books’ series experiments with repurposing existing OA content which is then remixed and recombined with new texts in books. These books remain open and editable, which is a feature that has been exploited by a number of other OA books from library- and scholar-led publishers (Open Book Publishers, 2019a). The potential of digital publishing has also been used to host embedded music in books (e.g. Hobson from Open Book Publishers, 2019b), embedded audio in other languages (Open Book Publishers, 2019c), while The Goldsmiths Press is looking to expand its repertoire to include the publication of apps (Goldsmiths, University of London, 2019). When it

comes to the mechanics of publishing, we can observe experiments in peer review, which include exploring the potential of optional open peer reviewing practices (Mattering Press; Media Commons Press) and forms of ‘collaborative review’ involving ongoing dialogue with in-house editors (e.g. electric.press; see Adema & Stone, 2017, p.59-60).

We can also observe experiments with backend publishing practices: the ScholarLed consortium of publishers is, for instance, developing a shared metadata platform that will allow the creation of a catalogue containing book across different publishers. Open Book Publishers, a key part of this group, has itself led the way in developing a variety of processes for enhancing discoverability, providing highly detailed and openly accessible metrics to authors and readers. It is also possible to observe the creation of new business models that both draw on and deepen forms of community engagement (punctum books), new partnerships between libraries, academic institutions and publishers (punctum books, The Goldsmiths Press, UCL Press, Westminster University Press, LSE Press, Kriterium and University of Huddersfield Press), and collaborations between universities (White Rose Press).

Challenge 3: Quality

Questions around quality in relation to new formats have been occurring for many years. It could be argued that this is a result of resistance to change. For example, Stone (2017) notes that attitudes of many authors to open access mirror the attitudes of authors to e-resources in the 1990’s (Budd & Connaway, 1997; Speier et al., 1999), which identified that faculty held a “prevalent belief that electronic journals were lower quality than print journals” (McClanahan et al., 2010, p.210). In the UK, this attitude was also expressed with specific reference to open access monographs in the evidence submitted to the *Consultation on open access in the post-2014 Research Excellence Framework* (HEFCE, 2013).

Quality is of course a complex attribute that depends on discourse and point of departure. It should also be mentioned that traditional scholarly journal and book publishing has been lacking transparency for a long time, something that is not considered to contribute to some aspects of quality. Often processes have been an internal affair and in many cases still are. Only in the last 20 years have we seen a move towards more information about review processes (e.g. ARL - ‘Temple Principles’, 2000; AAUP, 2016), whereas the OAPEN project, which launched its platform in 2010, has been a good example of mandating transparency of its members’ editorial processes (OAPEN, n.d.). This growing transparency is of huge importance in order to tackle the quality debate around open access and more specifically open access for books. Open access book publishers and related services have been forced to address the issues around quality because of accusations of, amongst other reasons, vanity publishing. This has led to a much faster move to more transparency of editorial and review processes, and a

discussion about standardisation of the peer-review process for books similar to the journals model.

Credibility and Trust

“The ‘predatory publishing’ label is often linked to open access in order to discredit it” (Joy, 2018). Issues with predatory publishing have gathered more attention when former librarian Jeffrey Beall created his blacklist in 2008 with in some cases obvious examples of dubious publishers and journals. He ceased his activities early 2017 but the term predatory publisher and/or journal still receives attention. It is however still a very problematic term. As Smith states, “the use of ‘predatory’ as an umbrella term for all kinds of abuses hides the difference between practices that really are ‘ruthlessly exploitative’ and those that may well grow out of mere inexperience or lack of competence” (Smith, 2017, p.4). Others are commercializing this black- and whitelisting of publishers and journals, which in itself raises a lot of new issues about transparency (e.g. Cabell’s, 2017). However, it should be mentioned that the majority of predatory publishing centres on journal publishing, possibly because of the financial incentive caused by the Article Processing Charge (APC) model. Predatory book publishing or vanity publishing does exist (Collins, 2010) but many of these presses are completely unconnected to open access publishing. They often sell printed books (and in particular publish theses) without any quality control or adding editorial value. In addition, there may be additional publishing costs involved and the author often loses all rights to their work.

Establishing credibility and trust for open access publishers seems to be much more difficult because of the very traditional marketplace for books often based on prestige of the big traditional publishing houses and their brands. Currently there are not many good mechanics in place for starting open access journals and book publishers to become credible quickly, since the current system of assessment is all based on traditional quality indicators - like the Journal Impact Factor, and other rewarding mechanisms with a bias towards a certain type of publications.

The frequency that the term predatory publishing is used is a potential threat for new established academic- and library-led presses, which need to prove themselves first, particularly regarding the vanity press accusation. However, the presumption of new open access presses being of lower quality suggests again, that fear of change may be a factor rather than the format/model. However, there are also additional real concerns and these can be addressed with greater transparency regarding publishing practices, pricing and peer-review. There are indications of quality that all NUPs and other open access publishers could adopt, such as membership of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE, 2019) and/or the Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA, 2019) and the registration of journals in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ, 2019) and monographs in the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB, 2019).

Peer review is one way, but by no means the only way of ensuring quality. Reviewers are overworked in the traditional process and one solution could be to experiment with new models of peer review. Many academic- and library-led presses (i.e. Goldsmiths Press) have been the ones to open up the discussion on what quality is and how it is established, also focusing on supporting authors to make their publications better rather than focusing mainly on review criteria and procedures.

Challenge 4: Discoverability and dissemination

There is a perception that OA publishing is easily discoverable via Google and services such as DOAB, which makes open access content (for those that have passed the selection criteria) discoverable through library web scale discovery systems. However, one area of discovery has proved difficult to achieve, that of the library supply chain and reading lists or required reading. For example, Adema and Stone (2017) noted a number of comments regarding issues with discovery and dissemination with regards to the library supply chain from library- and academic-led publishing initiatives.

Open access publishers in general have difficulty accessing the commercial channels that library acquisition departments use to buy print and e-book content. Libraries tend to use approved library suppliers, which often do not list OA monographs, indeed, if they do, they often only list the copy available for purchase and not the free version.

In light of these comments, the Jisc report (Adema & Stone, 2017) made two recommendations. Firstly, that best practices in metadata were drawn up due to the various levels of maturity of metadata quality at NUPs and academic-led publishing initiatives. This view was confirmed at a European level by the Knowledge Unlatched report on visibility of metadata to the OPERAS project, which stated that “[t]he metadata held and managed by OPERAS partners is inconsistent and variable in quality. Collecting and aggregating data from multiple OPERAS partners was a challenge due to inconsistency in bibliographic metadata processes and formats” (Neylon et al., 2018).

The second recommendation was to provide support to these publishing initiatives in the area of distribution and dissemination to libraries in order to ensure a consistent approach and to give presses an entry point into the library supply chain. In order to progress these issues at a UK level, a workshop was held in 2018 to discuss the problem statement that, “OA publishers have difficulty accessing the channels that library acquisition departments use to buy print and e-book content” (Stone, 2018). The workshop brought together experts from library- and academic-led publishing initiatives, book suppliers and distributors, metadata suppliers, libraries and other experts in OA publishing for the first time. The group shared their experiences in

order to fully understand the problem from all sides and as a result the experts around the table agreed four key areas that needed to be taken forward in order to progress the resolution of issues around dissemination and discovery in the library supply chain. These included two practical areas, the library supply chain and metadata and two aspirational areas, cultural change in the acquisition process and new forms of content.

Defining the library supply chain

It was agreed that workflows and costs in the library supply chain need to be mapped in order for all parties to understand where they fit in as part of the process and also the costs involved and who needs to support this. For example, costs in creating metadata and who pays these costs.

Metadata

One of the key issues identified in the workshop was the confusion that existed, particularly amongst the open access publishers, about which types of metadata to use and when. This is not a symptom of a less professional approach as many of the issues were due to certain metadata schema not being able to mark a publication as open access. For example, it was noted that many traditional publishers also fell foul of this barrier. There was agreement that, although standards existed for each type of metadata, there was a need to agree a minimum metadata requirement that could be reproduced across all schema and that this was handled as one process. It is hoped that any future work will build upon that of the Jisc/OAPEN metadata model for OA monographs, which was “[d]eveloped in consultation with research funders, academics and institutional staff and OA monograph publishers, the model recommends a provisional list of metadata for OA book publishers and other stakeholders” (Snijder, 2016, p.1). The idea of a minimum metadata requirement was also put forward as part of the technical infrastructure workshop at the Knowledge Exchange workshop on open access and monographs in November 2018, it is hoped that a roadmap will follow in the near future (Adema, 2019).

Cultural change

Conversations between the stakeholders led to a suggestion from the libraries present on the day that there was an opportunity for cultural change regarding library collection development and management policies. It was felt that a change was needed in order to address the issue of ‘acquiring’ zero cost monographs. This piece of work will be developed further during 2019.

New forms of content

The fourth area for further discussion centred around new forms of content. Issues with discovery of the long form monographs in open access is only the start of the process. If, as hoped, open access helps develop new forms of content,

dissemination to the library market will have to be addressed. Work with the library supply chain needs to lay the foundations for the dissemination and discovery of innovation forms of publishing.

These themes are starting to be addressed by library- and academic-led publishing initiatives and others. In particular, through the work of ScholarLed (2018), which has launched a project looking directly at discovery and dissemination.

Conclusion

Although Plan S may appear to imply that open access for monographs will take longer than the transition to OA for journals (cOAlition S, 2019) the academic community needs to be prepared well in advance for cOAlition S to implement a mandate for monographs. Lessons need to be learned around the 'announcement' of a UK mandate by the former HEFCE at the 2018 Redux conference, which had in fact been indicated well in advance during 2016, "HEFCE are signaling an intention to introduce Open Access for monographs after 2021 to the REF (or its equivalent)" (Tanner, 2016, p.34), which was followed by a consultation document released in December 2016 (HEFCE, 2016, pp.36-38).

This caused widespread consternation and fallout in the academic community and is partly behind the reasons for a panel session at the 2018 LIBER conference (2018) and this paper.

Plan S should be a rallying cry for to open access presses to prepare. It is therefore timely and of great importance that a statement signed by over 40 publishers in the humanities and social sciences worldwide on the Plan S implementation guidelines was published before the deadline of the consultation by cOAlition S. This statement concludes that there is an "urgent need for transparent dialogue between all parties - funders, associations, libraries, journal editors, individual academics, publishers" (PlanSinHSS, 2019). We would like to add library- and academic-led presses to this list as well.

In conclusion, we argue that library- and academic-led publishers can provide the same reliable services as traditional publishers by using skill sets that are already represented in the academic organisations. Many of the skill sets required to produce innovation, sustainable publishing models are already in existence in these smaller open access publishing initiatives. Furthermore, best practice, which addresses perceptions around quality, scale and quality is also evident.

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Competing Interest

Jeroen Sondervan is publishing consultant at Uopen Journals. LIBER Quarterly is published in the Uopen Journals programme. Sofie Wennström is working as a Managing Editor for books and journals at Stockholm University Press, and is involved in the LIBER Open Access Working Group.

All authors declare that there are no further competing interests.

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